

USING VIDEO MATERIALS AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS OF CLASSROOMS.

Nurbekova Shakhnoza Sheralievna
Assistant at "Uzbek and foreign languages department at
Tashkent institute of Textile and light industry

Abstract: This article reveals benefits of using video materials in EFL classes, as well as to show that by using appropriate video material teachers can improve and ensure studentcenteredness, rise students' engagement during activities, be more active, motivated and confident in their communicative language competence.

Key words: video materials, authentic material, communicative language teaching, productive and receptive skills.

INTRODUCTION: It is widely known that audiovisual materials stimulate and facilitate the teaching of foreign languages. All audiovisual media contribute positively to language learning, at least if they are applied at the right time and in the right place. In teaching a foreign language and in the process of learning it, the student uses the visual and auditory canals to perceive information, but the visual, nevertheless, remains the basis of learning. For example, an American educator, W.Rivers, argues that these learning tools are significantly contribute to the understanding of foreign language culture, providing compensatory contact with a native speaker, through audio and visual means. Using video materials in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms can be highly effective for language learning. Here are some key points to consider about the effectiveness of using video materials in EFL classrooms:

1. Visual and auditory input: Videos provide a rich source of authentic audiovisual materials that expose learners to natural speech patterns, intonation, body language, and contextual information. This helps improve listening comprehension skills and aids in acquiring correct pronunciation and language structures.

2. Contextualized language learning: Videos often present language within meaningful contexts, allowing learners to understand how vocabulary, grammar, and social interactions are used in real-life situations. This enhances learners' ability to use English in authentic contexts and reinforces their understanding of language in a meaningful way.

3. Cultural exposure: Videos offer a window into the target culture, allowing learners to explore and understand different cultural aspects such as customs, traditions, and social norms. This promotes intercultural competence and helps learners develop a global perspective.

4. Engagement and motivation: Videos can captivate learners' interest and motivation by providing an enjoyable and interactive learning experience. Engaging visuals, storytelling, and dynamic presentation can create a fun and stimulating learning environment, fostering learner participation and active engagement.

5. Authenticity and real-world language use: Videos expose learners to authentic language use, including colloquial expressions, slang, and natural language variations. This bridges the gap between classroom learning and real-world language use, helping learners develop communicative competence.

6. Multimodal learning: Videos combine visual, auditory, and sometimes textual elements, catering to different learning styles and preferences. This multimodal approach accommodates a range of learners and enhances their understanding and retention of the language. To maximize the effectiveness of video materials in EFL classrooms, it is important to choose videos that are appropriate for the learners' proficiency level, content that aligns with the learning objectives, and videos that are engaging and relevant to learners' interests. Additionally, it is crucial to supplement video viewing with pre-viewing, during-viewing, and post-viewing activities to enhance comprehension and language practice. One of the most effective means of teaching a foreign language is video materials. In recent years, the use of video in foreign language classes is constantly growing due to the increasing use of communicative teaching methods. The video shows the peculiarities of the behavior

of people inherent in their culture, which, in turn, introduces various communicative situations to the lesson. An important factor is that it helps to understand the language, since a limited vocabulary can make even the simplest task difficult to complete. The video helps to understand the meaning of some previously unknown words, thanks to the shown situation, which proves the words that the image is worth thousand words. The huge advantage of using video in teaching foreign languages is that it really provides authentic material. Obviously, the practical use of video, as a rule, does not cause any special difficulties and the teacher can logically choose the time of its use in the lesson, as well as stop it, continue watching and review the entire fragment or some part of it. Any video clip can be used for intensive study of a foreign language. Implementation of video materials during the lesson ameliorate productive and receptive skills and language competences at the same time. According to the communicative language teaching approach, language teachers need to think about using a variety of using authentic materials in the EFL classroom for the purpose of encouraging communication and interaction among peers. Video serves as an incentive to learn foreign languages. Maneekul conducted a study on using authentic material and tasks to enhance listening skill for undergraduate students majoring in English. The results revealed that students' listening skill increased to a higher level when using authentic materials and tasks after watching native speakers' video programs. Students are given the opportunity to apply and expand their knowledge on unfamiliar authentic material. Therefore, students can put themselves in the vivid atmosphere created by the video materials and understand the pragmatics of the language used by the characters. Compared with traditional English teaching, such courses truly put into practice the student-centered teaching strategies. When students realize that they are able to understand authentic foreign language, they increase their self-esteem and motivation to study the subject.

Moreover, when teachers bring video materials into their English classrooms, students can directly acquire a great amount of cultural background information and emotional attitudes about the learning materials. Video materials can bring cultural

information to the EFL which is an important aspect in learning a foreign language. Richards confirms the importance of using videos in EFL classroom on the basis that "they provide authentic cultural information about the target culture". An important fact is that authentic materials, particularly movies and video clips are more suitable for teaching the cultural aspect of the target language. Movies and video clips are a great authentic and reliable way of teaching students the cultural aspects of the target language. The teacher plays a key role in the use of video as an auxiliary tool for teaching a foreign language, as it is responsible for creating an enabling environment for learning. The teacher should consider video material as a useful learning tool, not as a rival at class. It cannot replace the teacher, because it can only teach what is recorded on the medium, which makes the learning process so attractive. It is safe to say that the teacher is as effective as the videos in teaching through video, because he is the only one who allows students to understand what they see and hear using some communicative techniques.

According to River's research, language teachers like video because it motivates learners, brings the real world into the classroom, contextualizes language naturally and enables learners to experience authentic language. Students like it because video presentations are interesting, challenging, and stimulating to watch". It is hypothesized that video material can be applied as authentic material input and as a motivational tool. In general, students find the experience of using video material to be interesting, relevant, beneficial and somewhat motivating in class. As a result, it may be suggested that both teachers and students can be involved in creative ways to incorporate different video materials in a variety of classroom activities to enhance learning outcomes and provide a positive classroom environment.

PEFERENCES

1. Gilmore, A. Authentic materials and authenticity in foreign language learning. Language teaching, 40 (2), 97-118.2007

2. Maneekul, J. (2002). Use of authentic material and tasks to enhance English Listening

3. Skill for undergraduate students majoring in teaching English at Faculty of Education, Chiang Mai University. Unpublished master's thesis, Chiang Mai University

4. Rivers, W.M. Teaching Foreign-Language Skills/ W.M. Rivers. - Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1981.